

An Analysis of Free-Edge Delamination in Laminated Composite under Uniform Axial Strain

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ABSTRACT

The free edge delamination of laminated composites under uniaxial strain is investigated in this study. The laminate is modeled as a set of anisotropic layers with isotropic adhesive layers. Interlaminar stresses and in-plane stresses before and after delamination are calculated using a two-dimensional finite difference method. The strain level at the initiation of delamination and the relation between delamination and first ply failure are evaluated by utilizing failure theories. Computational results are compared with experimental results and discussed in terms of the initiation and growth of delamination.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination is one of the most frequently encountered types of failure in fiber-reinforced composites. This phenomenon is unique to composites and is not commonly found in metals and polymers. Since interlaminar strength is very low and interlaminar stresses are usually high, delamination is a matrix dominant failure occurring between composite layers. It takes the form of separation of plies and is commonly initiated at geometric boundaries or defects such as micro-cracks and voids. It causes structural degradation, stiffness reduction and failure at stresses well below the strength levels expected for defect free material. Therefore predictions of the useful life for composite structures require a comprehensive understanding of the material response to delaminations.

The knowledge of the stress behavior near a free edge is necessary to investigate free edge delamination. Stress distributions for straight free edges have been obtained by many authors [1-4]. A mathematical treatment of delamination crack was presented for the isotropic case [5]. The mechanics and failure modes of delamination initiated from a surface flaw in an angle-ply fiber-reinforced composite was presented by S. S. Wang [6]. A strain energy release rate approach was employed to study the initiation and growth of delamination crack [7-8]. Reifsneider, et al. [9] predicted the initiation of free edge delamination using interlaminar normal stress. But Alexander Harris, et al. [10] observed that delamination failure occurred due to combined interlaminar stresses rather than interlaminar normal stress alone. However, many fundamental problems associated with delamination still remain unclear.

FORMULATION

The laminate of Figure 1 is modeled as a set of anisotropic layers with isotropic matrix layers. The analysis of this model will be used on the following assumptions;

The anisotropic layers and isotropic matrix layers are homogeneous and linear elastic. The thickness of matrix layers is small compared to that of anisotropic layers, hence the matrix layers may be treated as a shear spring. The surface shear transmitted through the matrix is regarded as a body force. The laminate is mid-plane symmetric and the anisotropic layers are assumed to undergo only in-plane deformation.

In this model a delamination crack is simulated by releasing shear springs. The unique feature of this model is the capability to propagate multistrip delaminations without difficulties compared to past works [5-8] considering the complex interfacial crack.

Governing Equations

The following differential equations express the equilibrium conditions for the anisotropic layers;

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x^{(i)}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}^{(i)}}{\partial y} + \frac{\tau_{xz}^{(i-1)} - \tau_{xz}^{(i)}}{h_0} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{xy}^{(i)}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_y^{(i)}}{\partial y} + \frac{\tau_{yz}^{(i-1)} - \tau_{yz}^{(i)}}{h_0} = 0 \quad (i=1,2,\dots,N) \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_x^{(i)}$, $\sigma_y^{(i)}$ and $\tau_{xy}^{(i)}$ are in-plane stresses in the i-th layer, $\tau_{xz}^{(i)}$ and $\tau_{yz}^{(i)}$ are surface shear stresses acting on the faces of i and (i+1)-th layer and h_0 is anisotropic layer thickness. If i is equal to 1 (or N), the surface shear stresses acting on the upper (or lower) face are zero.

$$\tau_{xz}^{(0)} = \tau_{yz}^{(0)} = 0$$

$$\tau_{xz}^{(N)} = \tau_{yz}^{(N)} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Assumption above gives the following continuity conditions;

$$u^{(i)} - u^{(i+1)} = \frac{h_m}{G} \cdot \tau_{xz}^{(i)}$$

$$v^{(i)} - v^{(i+1)} = \frac{h_m}{G} \cdot \tau_{yz}^{(i)} \quad (i=1,2,\dots,N-1) \quad (3)$$

where $u^{(i)}$ and $v^{(i)}$ are displacement components in the x, y directions respectively, G is shear modulus of matrix layer and h_m is matrix layer thickness. The stress-strain relationship for the anisotropic layers is expressed as;

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x^{(i)} \\ \sigma_y^{(i)} \\ \tau_{xy}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11}^{(i)} & \bar{Q}_{12}^{(i)} & \bar{Q}_{16}^{(i)} \\ \bar{Q}_{21}^{(i)} & \bar{Q}_{22}^{(i)} & \bar{Q}_{26}^{(i)} \\ \bar{Q}_{61}^{(i)} & \bar{Q}_{62}^{(i)} & \bar{Q}_{66}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x^{(i)} \\ \epsilon_y^{(i)} \\ \gamma_{xy}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (i=1,2,\dots,N) \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{Q}_{ij}^{(i)}$ is transformed reduced stiffness matrix in layer i and strain-displacement relationship is as follows;

$$\epsilon_x^{(i)} = \frac{\partial u^{(i)}}{\partial x}, \quad \epsilon_y^{(i)} = \frac{\partial v^{(i)}}{\partial y}, \quad \gamma_{xy}^{(i)} = \frac{\partial u^{(i)}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^{(i)}}{\partial x} \quad (5)$$

Substituting (2)-(5) into (1), the governing equations in terms of the displacements are obtained

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\bar{Q}_{11}^{(i)} D_{xx} + 2\bar{Q}_{16}^{(i)} D_{xy} + \bar{Q}_{66}^{(i)} D_{yy} \right] u^{(i)} \\ & + \left[\bar{Q}_{16}^{(i)} D_{xx} + (\bar{Q}_{12}^{(i)} + \bar{Q}_{66}^{(i)}) D_{xy} + \bar{Q}_{26}^{(i)} D_{yy} \right] v^{(i)} \\ & + \frac{G}{h_o \cdot h_m} \left[u^{(i-1)} - 2u^{(i)} + u^{(i+1)} \right] = 0 \quad (i=1,2,\dots,N) \quad (6) \\ & \left[\bar{Q}_{16}^{(i)} D_{xx} + (\bar{Q}_{12}^{(i)} + \bar{Q}_{66}^{(i)}) D_{xy} + \bar{Q}_{26}^{(i)} D_{yy} \right] u^{(i)} \\ & + \left[\bar{Q}_{66}^{(i)} D_{xx} + 2\bar{Q}_{26}^{(i)} D_{xy} + \bar{Q}_{22}^{(i)} D_{yy} \right] v^{(i)} + \frac{G}{h_o \cdot h_m} \left[v^{(i-1)} - 2v^{(i)} + v^{(i+1)} \right] = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The symbol D indicates partial differential operator with respect to its subscripts. Since interlaminar normal stress, σ_z , can not be found from the solutions satisfying differential equations (6), Pagano and Pipes [11] method was used to obtain an approximate distribution of interlaminar normal stress at the free edge.

Failure Criterion

The relation between delamination and the first ply failure may be considered by applying failure criterion to anisotropic layers and isotropic matrix layers respectively. Maximum distortion energy criterion is applied to the matrix layer,

$$\left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left[(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 + (\sigma_y - \sigma_z)^2 + (\sigma_z - \sigma_x)^2 \right] + 3(\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} = \sigma_{yp} \quad (7)$$

where σ_{yp} is yield stress in simple tension test and assumed to about 69Mpa for epoxy [9]. This criterion is helpful in identifying likely delamination sites rather than determining delamination onset because of the stress singularity [4] at the free edge. For anisotropic layers, Tsai-Wu tensor theory [12] is applied

$$F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j = 1 \quad (i, j=1, \dots, 6) \quad (8)$$

Since stresses vary in the y and z directions, the predicted mean axial stress for onset of failure at the center and edge regions may be different. Hence the failure criterion (8) must be applied to center and edge region respectively.

Energy Release Rate

The energy release rate, G , is defined for a delamination propagation as,

$$G = \lim_{\Delta l \rightarrow 0} \left[U(l) - U(l+\Delta l) \right] / \Delta l \quad (9)$$

where U is the strain energy of the laminate per unit thickness in the x-direction and expressed as,

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int \sigma_{ij} \epsilon_{ij} dydz \quad (10)$$

The energy release rate, G, is calculated for the condition that the length of delamination changes from ℓ to $\ell + \Delta\ell$ by holding the uniaxial strain constant.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The material region under study can be reduced by symmetry condition to a half of the laminate cross sectional region in the y-z plane as shown in Figure 2. Such a two-dimensional model is possible on the basis that the delamination crack extends along the entire length of the laminate, in agreement with the fact that the stresses are independent of x under uniform axial strain, almost instantaneously upon its formation. The continuous region is replaced by a rectangular grid of material points with constant square grid spacing. In this work, central difference operators are employed in the whole region by locating fictitious points on one grid space outside the boundary along y=0 and y=b axis. The fictitious points are set to imply proper boundary conditions. The boundary conditions are;

$$\begin{aligned} y = b ; \quad \sigma_y(y,z) &= 0 \\ \tau_{xy}(y,z) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

From the anti-symmetry condition [1,3]

$$\begin{aligned} y = 0 ; \quad u(y,z) &= -u(-y,z) \\ v(y,z) &= -v(-y,z) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

In this model, delamination is assumed to initiate when the equivalent stress of matrix layer satisfies equation(7). The effect of delamination is simulated by substituting zero shear modulus to the delaminated matrix layer and the length of delamination is assumed to be one grid space.

EXPERIMENTS

To measure the applied axial strain at the onset of delamination, two sets of delamination prone laminates, $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ and $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$, were used. The test specimens were T-305 graphite epoxy coupons (Table 1) with 25.4mm width, 0.125mm ply-thickness and 200mm length parallel to the applied loading. The coupons were machined from a panel and Al-Tabs were bonded to both ends. The tests were performed at a rate of approximately 3mm/min in a 10 Ton-capacity Instron-machine(Model-1350). During tests both the unloaded edges were visually observed with a optical microscope. A recording of the axial strain versus applied load was made for each coupon to check the initiation of delamination. The strain for incipient delamination was taken as that strain corresponding to a discernible change in slope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows the comparison of results along the interface at $z=h/2$. It is noted that the present analysis shows good agreement with Pipes and Pagano[1]. As/3501-6 graphite-epoxy (Table 1) quasi-isotropic laminates were used for the analysis of delamination. Figure 4 shows that there is a tensile normal stress, σ_z , through the thickness with a maximum at the middle plane for $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ and $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$. But we would expect delamination to occur at $z=\pm h_0$ due to combined effects of interlaminar shear stresses and interlaminar normal stress. From the analysis, delamination was predicted to occur prior to the first ply

failure. But from experimental observation we found that delamination and transverse cracking in 90° plies initiate at similar strain level of about 4.7 to 6.0×10^{-3} . It suggests that delamination may interact with transverse cracking. The reason of this phenomenon can be explained by the redistribution of laminate stress normalized by average in-plane stress, $\bar{\sigma}_x$. Figure 5 shows the increase of in-plane stress, σ_x , after delamination in 90° plies. Such a tendency with high interlaminar tensile stress, σ_z , near free edge may be the cause of transverse cracking in 90° plies. During experiment, this phenomenon has been observed in both laminates, but the stacking sequence $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ has a lower delamination strain than the sequence $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ because of higher interlaminar stresses. Figure 6 and Figure 7 show that interlaminar shear stress, τ_{yz} , decreases after delamination. The decrease of interlaminar shear stress, τ_{yz} , may interact with the decrease of in-plane stress, σ_y , in adjacent plies. Similar trend can be observed for interlaminar shear stress, τ_{xz} , and in-plane stress, τ_{xy} . But we did not find a change of interlaminar normal stress, σ_z , during delamination. This can be explained from the fact that the approximate method [11] evaluates interlaminar normal stress, σ_z , from the in-plane stress, σ_y , at the center region which is independent of delamination. From the fact that in-plane stress, σ_x , decreases after delamination near the free edge in all laminas except 90° plies, we would expect a decrease of laminate stiffness. This tendency has been observed during experiment and used as a criterion for edge delamination. Figure 8 shows the pattern of delamination growth. This results suggest that delamination may be stable growth; it does not spread completely across the specimen under static loading condition. Finally, it will be worthwhile to pursue a more accurate criterion such as critical energy release rate to predict delamination strain which is not affected by the grid space because of stress singularity [4].

CONCLUSIONS

A simple approach to consider delamination and first ply failure has been developed using two-dimensional finite difference method. Results of this show that the transverse cracking of 90° plies may interact with delamination and stiffness reduction is caused due to delamination. From the strain energy release rate we found that some stable delamination growth occurs.

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TABLE 1. UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE CONSTANTS

	AS/3051-6	T-305
	Graphite Epoxy	Graphite Epoxy
Elastic Constants		
E_{11} (Mpa)	144100	132500
E_{22} (Mpa)	9730	9810
G_{12} (Mpa)	4480	3550
ν_{12}	0.21	0.26
Interlaminar Constant		
G (Mpa)	1280	1280
Strength Constants		
F_1 (Gpa) ⁻¹	0	0
F_{11} (Gpa) ⁻²	0.268	0.38
F_2 (Gpa) ⁻¹	11.26	13.46
F_{22} (Gpa) ⁻²	98.98	141.7
F_{66} (Gpa) ⁻²	51.53	73.1
F_{12} (Gpa) ⁻²	-2.58	-3.67

Fig.1. Laminated Composite geometry.

Fig.2. Finite difference representation.

Fig.3. Stresses along the interface at $z = h/2$.

Fig.4 Interlaminar normal stress distribution at the free edge.

Fig. 5 Stresses distribution for 90° lamina in $0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ_s$ laminate.

Fig. 6. Interlaminar shear stress distribution along the interface.

Fig. 7. Interlaminar shear stress distribution along the interface.

Fig. 8. Strain energy release rate as a function of delamination length.